

SCIENTIFIC AND THEORETICAL ANALYSIS OF THE PROCEDURE FOR CONDUCTING "SOCIAL PREVENTION WEEK" IN THE MAHALLAS OF THE REPUBLIC

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Abstract: This study provides a comprehensive analysis of the legal, organizational, and social aspects of the procedure for conducting "Social Prevention Week" in the mahallas of the republic. It highlights the content and essence of the goals and objectives defined in the Regulation, the mechanism for organizing the week, the system of interdepartmental cooperation, targeted social prevention measures, as well as the importance of monitoring and reporting mechanisms. "Social Prevention Week" is assessed as a comprehensive initiative aimed at the early prevention of offenses in mahallas, raising legal awareness and culture among the population, and identifying and solving social problems. The conclusions of the study indicate that the full and systematic implementation of this procedure will help stabilize the criminogenic situation in mahallas.

Keywords: social prevention, social prevention week, mahalla institute, early prevention of offenses, criminogenic situation, interagency cooperation, targeted prevention, monitoring, accountability, legal culture.

Combating crime is one of the priority tasks of modern public administration. However, the possibility of reducing crime only through punitive measures is limited, and a preventive approach aimed at eliminating its root causes and conditions is of paramount importance. From this point of view, the systematic organization and implementation of social prevention measures at the mahalla level is of great importance. The procedure for holding the "Week of Social Prevention" in the mahallas of the republic manifests itself as an institutional mechanism aimed precisely at this goal.

The concept of "Social Prevention Week" is defined as a set of organizational, practical, and methodological measures, the main goal of which is the early prevention of offenses by increasing the effectiveness of social prevention in mahallas. Crime is often associated with social problems - unemployment, family conflicts, social inequality, lack of legal knowledge. Therefore, within the framework of social prevention week, it is important to implement measures aimed at identifying and eliminating these factors.

According to the Regulation, the organization and conduct of the week are mandatory for all state bodies, local authorities, and local self-government bodies. This indicates that the preventive process is complex and interdepartmental in nature. In the fight against crime, the activities of law enforcement agencies alone are insufficient, cooperation in the spheres of healthcare, education, social protection, employment, and finance is required. The involvement of all subjects in this area in the organization of the week will increase the effectiveness of prevention.

The submission by district (city) khokims of proposals for holding a week based on the analysis of the criminogenic situation in the region represents an analytical model of

prevention. Coverage of "red" category mahallas, areas with a high level of female crime, places with a high incidence of drug and alcohol addiction, as well as mahallas with conflict families, will ensure a targeted approach. This will allow for the rational use of resources and strengthen attention to high-risk areas.

In the process of organizing the week, a clear mechanism, executors, deadlines, and financial sources of the measures will be indicated, which will strengthen management discipline. Based on the order, a mechanism of responsibility and control will be formed by holding the week, creating an organizing committee and an interdepartmental working group. This ensures the formal and systematic implementation of preventive measures.

Announcing the week through the media and social networks will raise public awareness and ensure public participation. Considering that the fight against crime is a common task not only of state bodies, but also of society, involving the population in the prevention process is of great importance. The formation of a sense of belonging to the mahalla among citizens and the strengthening of an intolerant attitude towards offenses will increase the social effectiveness of prevention.

Within the framework of the week, measures will be taken to work individually with social prevention facilities, solve their problems on the spot, provide legal advice, organize job fairs, and involve them in entrepreneurship. These measures are aimed at reducing the root causes of crime by eliminating social problems. Also, the goal is to attract young people to a healthy lifestyle and prevent deviant behavior through cultural and sports events.

Daily analysis of events and preparation of the final report form a system of monitoring and evaluation. This serves as a basis for improving preventive measures in the future. Coverage of reports in the mass media ensures transparency and strengthens public trust.

Thus, the procedure for holding the "Social Prevention Week" in the mahallas of the republic is a comprehensive system, including legal regulation, interdepartmental cooperation, and mechanisms for targeted social prevention and monitoring. Its effective implementation will contribute to the formation of a safe social environment in mahallas.

The procedure for holding the "Week of Social Prevention" in the mahallas of the republic manifests itself as an institutional mechanism for the practical organization of crime prevention. Modern criminological research emphasizes that the effectiveness of measures aimed at eliminating social factors in crime prevention depends on targeted work at the mahalla level [1]. From this point of view, the organization of "Social Prevention Week" on a legal basis, based on certain procedures and mechanisms, is an important condition for increasing the effectiveness of prevention.

A clear definition of the concept of "Social Prevention Week" in the general provisions of the Regulation ensures legal clarity. The fact that this week is defined as a set of organizational, practical, and methodological measures indicates the complex nature of prevention. International studies have shown that clear legal regulation of preventive programs increases their effectiveness [2]. Also, the definition of the participation of state bodies, local authorities, and public structures will strengthen the mechanism of interdepartmental cooperation.

The main goal of the Week is the early prevention of offenses by increasing the effectiveness of social prevention in mahallas. This goal is combined with the tasks of identifying the problems of social prevention facilities, raising the legal awareness and culture of the population, promoting a healthy lifestyle, and strengthening social solidarity in the

mahalla. Ensuring public participation in scientific research is noted as an important factor in crime prevention [3].

The submission by district (city) khokims of proposals for holding a week based on the analysis of the criminogenic situation represents an analytical model of prevention. Coverage of mahallas that have remained in the "red" category for three and five years will ensure a targeted approach. Scientific analysis has shown that directing resources to hazardous areas increases the effectiveness of prevention [4]. The indication of a specific mechanism, deadlines, and financial sources in the proposal ensures management discipline.

The organization of the week based on the orders of the khokims of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regions, and the city of Tashkent will strengthen the legal basis. Assigning the execution of the order to the khokims of districts (cities) will strengthen the principle of personal responsibility. The creation of an interdepartmental working group ensures comprehensive interaction. Studies have shown that multi-subject prevention models are effective in reducing crime [5].

Announcing the weekly through the mass media will increase public awareness. According to official statistics, there has been a decrease in offenses in areas where the public participated in preventive measures [6]. Holding events based on the principle of "Prosperous and Safe Mahalla" strengthens the social orientation of prevention.

Within the framework of the Week, targeted work with social prevention facilities and addressing their problems on the ground will be prioritized. The employment of the unemployed, their involvement in entrepreneurship, and the provision of financial assistance serve to reduce the economic factors of crime. International studies have noted a decrease in crime rates where economic stability has increased [7].

Labor fairs, legal consultations, and personal receptions strengthen public trust in government bodies. Daily analysis of events and reporting form a monitoring mechanism. Scientific sources emphasize that the monitoring and evaluation system is a necessary condition for the stable effectiveness of preventive programs [8].

By organizing cultural and sports events, it is possible to create an atmosphere of intolerance towards offenses among young people and the population. Studies have noted that promoting a healthy lifestyle serves to prevent deviant behavior [9]. Holding awareness-raising events, uniting up to five mahallas, will allow for the effective use of resources.

Thus, the procedure for holding "Social Prevention Week" in the mahallas of the republic manifests itself as a comprehensive system combining legal, organizational, and social mechanisms. The full and effective implementation of this procedure will serve to stabilize the criminogenic situation in mahallas, prevent crime in a timely manner, and ensure the safety of citizens. Therefore, the following can be concluded:

Firstly, the organization of "Social Prevention Week" on the basis of legal order systematizes the prevention process and defines specific tasks for all subjects;

secondly, through a targeted approach to mahallas with a difficult criminogenic situation, the possibility of eliminating social problems and early prevention of offenses is created;

thirdly, the effectiveness and stability of preventive measures will be increased by ensuring interdepartmental cooperation and public participation;

fourthly, mechanisms for monitoring and reporting will allow for the assessment and improvement of the preventive process, which will serve the consistent stabilization of the criminogenic situation in mahallas.

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